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Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information is available at the end of the article.

Conference Abstract

THE ROLE OF SYED ABUL AALA MAUDUDI IN THE ISLAMIC RENAISSANCE MOVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In nineteenth and twentieth centuries, the Western imperialism attacked on the Muslim Ummah in different ways. In these times different Muslim thinkers replied to the west but introducing the religion of Islam as a complete system of life is a great achievement of Sayyid Abu'l-Ala Maududi and we merely see any other leader parallel to him. With his insight into the demands of the time and circumstances, he revived the tradition of ijihad and revived the new concept of renaissance in Islam. He also confronted the challenges facing Islamic civilization on a global scale with full intellectual and practical wisdom and steadfastness. He presents Islamic systems including political system as a viable concept in all individual and social spheres of life and as a competitor to Western civilization. Hence it is interpreted as the "Islamic Renaissance". For this reason, he also has the status of the founder of the thought of Political Islam. About the theory of the clash of civilizations, more than half of his thoughts consist of the comparison and competition between Western and Islamic civilizations. Western world considers and responsible him for terrorism, political Islam, and fundamentalism, and considers him a party in the clash of civilizations. In this regard, studying his thoughts is also an important topic, especially for the Western political world. Due to his universal influence, he is recognized as the most prominent thinker and leader presenting the political thought of Islam today. That is why, Dr. Mahmood Ahmed Ghazi, after an in-depth analysis of Syed Maududi's criticism of Western civilization and its philosophy of life, has emphasized the need

to make his criticism of the West as a subject of special study and discussion so that the evolution of Islamic thought in the twentieth century can be brought to the fore.

Keywords Civilization, education, clash of civilization, Islam

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